

Research Article

A clinico-epidemiological investigation of human Leptospirosis in the Panhala hill area of Maharashtra, focusing on agricultural and dairy farm- A Population Based Case Control Study

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Abstract

The clinico-epidemiological study, which focused on agricultural and dairy settings in the Panhala hill area of Maharashtra, was a beneficial method to studying the dynamics of human leptospirosis in that particular location. A population-based case-control research can shed light on the disease's risk factors and assist guide focused efforts for prevention and treatment.

In this study, we enroll individuals who have been diagnosed with leptospirosis (cases) and compare them with a control group of individuals without the disease. The study aim to collect data on various clinico-epidemiological factors to determine potential associations and risk factors for leptospirosis in the agricultural and dairy settings of the Panhala hill area. For the age group and gender, a total of 22 confirmed cases of leptospirosis were documented. Of the cases, the age group of 36–56 years accounted for 60% of them, followed by 15–35 years (40.9%) and 56+ years (12.5%). More than 81.81% lived in rural regions, with almost 68.18% working as farmers, followed by animal husbandry (22.72%) and daily wage jobs (9.09%) such as dairy work. In control there were Males 20 and 24 females.

By conducting a clinico-epidemiological investigation in the Panhala hill area, researchers can gain a better understanding of the local dynamics of leptospirosis transmission, identify specific risk factors in agricultural and dairy settings, and develop evidence-based strategies for prevention and control. The findings from such a study can contribute to the overall knowledge and public health response to leptospirosis in the region.

Keywords: Leptospirosis, clinico-epidemiological, Panhala, agricultural and dairy farm.

INTRODUCTION

Leptospirosis is an infectious disease affecting both animals and humans. It is the most widespread zoonotic infection in the world. It is easily spread from sick animals by urine, either directly or through infected soil or water. [1,2]. It can result in a self-limiting influenza-like sickness or a much more deadly condition. Weil disease is a condition that can lead to multiorgan failure and death.

Leptospirosis is caused by infection with the spirochete bacteria *Leptospira*. It is most commonly transmitted by exposure to infected animals' urine, either directly or through contact with urine-contaminated soil or water. Farm animals such as cattle, pigs, and horses are common carriers of Leptospirosis, but it may also be transmitted by wild animals such as raccoons and porcupines as well as domesticated dogs. [3-5]. The more than 160 species of animals found to carry the disease show no signs/symptoms if infected. They can be vectors of disease for several months after inoculation, sometimes never showing any signs/symptoms of infection. It tends to be an unreported disease because its symptoms mimic many other disease processes; however, the World Health Organization has estimated that there are 873,000 cases annually with over 40,000 deaths.[6,7]

In outpatient cases, antibiotics that may be used include doxycycline, amoxicillin, or ampicillin.[8,2]. In severe cases, renal, lung, and CNS involvement may occur and are associated with very high mortality. These patients need ICU admission and monitoring.[9-11]

It is especially rampant in southern, central, eastern and western India, where heavy monsoon, animal rearing practices, unplanned

urbanization and agrarian way of life predispose to this infection[12-18]. Leptospirosis has long been recognized as one of the foremost causes of acute febrile illness in those parts of the country[13,16]. Though similar conditions exist in the north, reports of this disease from north India are few and only of recent origin (two of them from our center) [19-23].

People living in tropical and subtropical countries are most affected with human leptospirosis where factors like environmental conditions, social, and cultural practices favors its transmission in addition to scarcity of resources for prompt diagnosis and treatment of cases.[24]

Once it enters into the human body, the leptospira spreads to major organs and after an incubation period ranging from 2 to 30 days the disease manifests with clinical features like muscle ache, headache, fever and chills, vomiting, nausea, and abdominal pain for around 4 to 7 days. Antileptospira-specific antibodies mainly of IgM type are produced as part of humoral immunity which can be detected by diagnostic tests like Microscopic Agglutination Test and Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbant Assay (ELISA).[25]

Exposure to contaminated urine of animal carriers or contact with contaminated soil or water either directly or indirectly results in disease transmission.[26]

Various studies have reported predominant risk factors for transmission of leptospirosis especially in tropical countries include people living in proximity cattle farms, farming job which involves walking and working with barefooted in paddy fields, sewers, and contact with flood waters.[27,28]

Figure 1. A flow diagram describing the spread of Leptospira and organisms in people and animals, demonstrating the disease's zoonotic relevance. Bacteria are excreted into the water and soil by the mammalian reservoir host, from which humans and animals (cattle, dogs, pigs, horses, and others) pick infection, and further shed organisms in the urine. Pathogen-containing urine further contaminates water and soil. Leptospirosis is considered an occupational health hazard because the farmers, personnel working in the slaughterhouse, veterinarians and other workers coming in close proximity to infected animals are prone to get the disease.[29]

Species	Sum of # of samples	Sum of Favorable	Prevalence %
Buffalo	1176	538	45.75
Cow	8398	2038	24.26
Dog	1039	271	26.08
Goat	2900	563	19.42
Human	4394	416	9.47
Pig	177	28	15.80
Rodents	60	24	40.00

Table 1. Prevalence (%) of species-wise livestock leptospirosis in India (total data of 2005- 2023) [29]

Panhala is a city and hill station municipal council (3177 feet above sea level) located 18 kilometers northwest of Kolhapur in the Kolhapur district of Maharashtra, India.

Panhala is the smallest city in Maharashtra, and as a Municipal Council, it is fast expanding.

Leptospirosis is more common in tropical locations than in temperate regions because leptospires may live longer in warm and humid settings. Countries where there are chances of exposure of the human population to infected animals have greater chances of infection in humans. *Leptospira* spp. has a vast host range due to their capacity to infect and survive in a variety of hosts. It is found in a wide range of wild, domesticated, and marine species. Rodents are a key reservoir host, but other species including cattle, pigs, and dogs may also function as carriers and sources of infection for other animals or people.[30]

Controlling rat infestation on farms and fencing to keep stray dogs out of the farm can be effective prevention strategies.[31] In humans and animals, infections can occur by coming in contact with infected water and soil.[32,33] Human-to-human transmission is seldom documented. Infected urine is the cause of infection for humans and animals who come into touch. Human leptospirosis risk factors mostly include occupational groups such as farmers, slaughterhouse workers, veterinarians, rice field workers, and animal handlers, as well as leisure activities such as swimming and hunting. Leptospirosis can be spread by the

semen of infected animals.[34] The combined mortality from multiple studies was estimated to be 11%. [35]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The District Government Hospital, and medical college hospitals Kolhapur recorded 22 probable cases of leptospirosis presenting with fever and jaundice between June 2021 and July 2022.

An IgM ELISA test was performed on 52 blood samples obtained from all suspected cases. Of these, 22 samples were found to be positive for the disease. The IgM ELISA test has a sensitivity of 85% and a specificity of 90%, and it can be used in conjunction with other tests such as the Microscopic Agglutination Test. [36-38]

Exclusion criteria: Participants having a history of viral diseases, such as Japanese encephalitis or dengue fever, were excluded from the study. Controls were people who had tested negative for the illness and lived in the same area.

Method

The current study was initiated with the approval of the institutional ethics committee. Data were collected through an interview

method using a questionnaire that included details of informed consent as well as information about sociodemographics, occupation, exposure history such as contact with contaminated water, skin injury, such as dairy disposal work, garbage and drainage facilities in and around the farmhouse, and animal and dairy farming details.

Statistical analysis

Collected data were analysed using SPSS 20.0

Ethical approval

The study was initiated with the approval of institutional ethics committee of Shri Vyankatesh hospital and Research Centre, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India

Results:

For the age group and gender, a total of 22 confirmed cases of leptospirosis were documented. Of the cases, the age group of 36–56 years accounted for 60% of them, followed by 15–35 years (40.9%) and 56+ years (12.5%). More than 81.81% lived in rural regions, with almost 68.18% working as farmers, followed by animal husbandry (22.72%) and daily wage jobs (9.09%) such as dairy work. In control there were Males 20 and 24 females.

Sample Size	52	Positives 22	% 42.03	Control 44
Age Group				
Less than 15	2	0	0	
15-35	22	9	40.90	
36-56	20	12	60	
56+	8	1	12.5	
Gender				
Male	15	10	66.66	20
Female	37	12	32.43	24
Living area				
Urban	10	4	18.18	
Rural	42	18	81.81	
Occupation				
Farmer	35	15	68.18	
Labour/daily wage work	10	02	9.09	
Animal Husbandry	7	05	22.72	

Table2: Seroreactivity frequency, by age and sex.

Clinical presentation	Children or age Less than 15	15-35	36-56	56+
Fever	0	9 (40.90%)	12 (54.54%)	1 (4.54%)
Jaundice	0	4 (18.18%)	9 (40.90%)	1 (4.54%)
Renal injury	0	6 (27.27%)	8 (36.36%)	0
Pulmonary injury	0	1 (4.54%)	2 (9.09%)	0
Stiff neck	0	8 (36.36%)	1 (4.54%)	1 (4.54%)
Meningitis	0	3 (13.63)	7 (31.81%)	0
Hepatitis, pancreatitis	0	0	0	0

Table3: Number and proportion of leptospirosis symptoms obtained in our study.

The individuals' symptoms were recorded. Fever: 54.54%; jaundice: 40.90%; stiff neck: 36.36%; and meningitis: 31.81%. Individuals who were exposed to flood water and garbage disposal on a farm, as well as animal buildings on a dairy farm, were shown to be additional risk factors.

Farming is a substantial occupation, with important risk factors identified as the occurrence of skin wounds or abrasions while working, as well as direct contact with dirt or water.

It also indicated a strong correlation between leptospirosis and probable environmental factors such as open water sources/waste disposal as a source of contamination and a lack of waste disposal facilities near the farm, animal house, and dairy house.

Discussion and Conclusion

Almost every year, this area receives rainfall for four to five months, beginning in June and ending in October. The majority of the patients in our study were between the ages of 18 and 65, indicating a potential risk of occupational exposure within this working age group.

Several studies have revealed considerable geographical variations in leptospirosis risk factors throughout the world. Our study found that the most common occupational risk factors for leptospirosis were skin wounds or abrasions at work, contact with water or mud during labor, and agricultural activities, which is comparable with findings in south Gujarat.

[39] and middle Andaman.[40] Studies done by Sahneh E[42] in north Iran and by Dewi PS in Indonesia[41] Similar outcomes were obtained about the exposure of wounded skin to stagnant water or dirt while working.

Leptospirosis is a bacterial disease that can pose a public health risk, particularly in specific areas and populations. It is caused by the *Leptospira* bacteria, which are often transferred to people by contact with water, soil, or food contaminated with infected animals' urine, such as rats, mice, or cattle.

The impact of leptospirosis on productive age groups is noteworthy because it can lead to serious health consequences and economic burdens. Productive age groups often engage in occupational or recreational activities that involve exposure to environments where the bacteria may be present, such as farming, construction work, or water-related activities. Therefore, understanding human behavioral factors and their role in leptospirosis prevention is crucial for effective public health interventions. behavioral factors that contribute to leptospirosis prevention include hygiene practices, personal protective measures, and awareness of the disease. For example, individuals can reduce their risk of infection by avoiding contact with potentially contaminated water or soil, wearing protective clothing and footwear in high-risk environments, and practicing good personal hygiene, such as hand washing. Additionally, raising awareness about leptospirosis and its transmission routes among

the population can help promote preventive behaviors.

It's important to note that leptospirosis prevention requires a multi-faceted approach that includes both individual actions and broader public health strategies. This may involve implementing rodent control measures, improving sanitation and infrastructure, and providing access to healthcare services for early diagnosis and treatment.

Our study's findings highlight the significance of considering human behavioral factors in the prevention and control of leptospirosis, particularly among the population in productive age groups. By targeting these factors, public health efforts can be more effective in reducing the burden of leptospirosis and protecting the health of the affected communities.

The identification of high-risk zones is also crucial for effective prevention efforts. By conducting surveillance activities and mapping out areas where leptospirosis is more prevalent, healthcare workers and public health authorities can prioritize resources and interventions in those specific regions. This can include implementing targeted health education campaigns, distributing preventive measures, and ensuring access to healthcare services for early diagnosis and treatment.

Surveillance activities by healthcare workers play a vital role in detecting and responding to cases of leptospirosis. Timely identification of cases can help initiate appropriate treatment, prevent further transmission, and provide valuable data for monitoring the disease. Surveillance systems can involve healthcare facilities reporting suspected or confirmed cases, laboratory testing, and monitoring of trends and outbreaks.

Overall, a comprehensive approach that combines integrated rodent control measures, identification of high-risk zones, and surveillance activities by healthcare workers can be highly beneficial in reducing the burden of leptospirosis. By targeting interventions and resources where they are needed the most, public health efforts can be optimized to

address this neglected tropical disease effectively.

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Availability of data and materials

The dataset analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on a reasonable request.

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